

Supplement: A Penalty-Free Pipeline for Direct Quantum-Annealer Portfolio Optimization

Luis Lozano

April 2026

This supplement accompanies the main manuscript and provides the validation-result tables cited in the text. Tables S1 and S2 report the out-of-sample financial metrics for the penalized/sparsified validation methods (dense reference, best-sparse threshold, top- k , domain-prior, and random baseline) together with a final row for the *penalty-free live-QPU pipeline* applied to the same 21 validation instances (12 equity, 9 betting) for apples-to-apples comparison. The penalty-free row uses the best live-QPU post-processed sample from Pegasus and Zephyr at chain strengths $\{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$. Table S1 reports equity realized Sharpe, Probabilistic Sharpe Ratio (PSR), mean minimum track record length (MinTRL), and mean out-of-sample track record length. Table S2 reports betting realized ROI, Brier score, and log loss. Tables S3–S4 list representative selected industries and selected betting outcomes together with their realized financial metrics (penalized/sparsified pipelines). All values are reproduced from the saved result tables under `results/real_data_full/plot_tables/validation_summary.csv`, `results/real_data_full/validation_real_data.csv`, and `results/real_data_full/penalty_free_validation.jsonl`.

Table S1: Equity validation summary. Sharpe and PSR are reported as means with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals from the saved validation summary table. MinTRL and track record length are arithmetic means over the saved validation-detail rows.

Method	Realized Sharpe		PSR	Mean MinTRL	Mean track record	
Dense reference	0.106	[0.066, 0.146]	0.600	[0.550, 0.647]	532.2	22.0
Best sparse: threshold	0.209	[0.149, 0.270]	0.705	[0.634, 0.773]	3041.9	20.8
Best sparse: top-k	0.022	[-0.027, 0.066]	0.526	[0.453, 0.596]	1200.4	23.1
Best sparse: domain prior	0.013	[-0.077, 0.126]	0.489	[0.364, 0.639]	61.0	21.8
Random baseline	0.056	[0.017, 0.100]	0.539	[0.476, 0.595]	7662.3	22.0
Penalty-free (live QPU)	0.035	[-0.083, 0.134]	0.535	[0.368, 0.683]	422.3	22.0

Table S2: Betting validation summary. ROI, Brier score, and log loss are reported as means with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals from the saved validation summary table.

Method	Realized ROI		Brier score		Log loss	
Dense reference	0.160	[0.041, 0.268]	0.165	[0.127, 0.203]	0.511	[0.427, 0.600]
Best sparse: domain prior	0.200	[0.035, 0.354]	0.140	[0.089, 0.204]	0.459	[0.330, 0.600]
Best sparse: threshold	-0.041	[-0.070, -0.011]	0.198	[0.193, 0.205]	0.584	[0.572, 0.598]
Best sparse: top-k	-0.021	[-0.515, 0.387]	0.114	[0.035, 0.222]	0.392	[0.195, 0.634]
Random baseline	-0.117	[-0.336, 0.110]	0.151	[0.116, 0.187]	0.467	[0.376, 0.560]
Penalty-free (live QPU)	0.090	[-0.103, 0.271]	0.148	[0.084, 0.224]	0.475	[0.334, 0.644]

Table S3: Representative equity validation window (`equities_20251231_n24`, eight selected industries). The sparse row is the saved `best_sparse:threshold` solution for this window.

Method	Selected industries	Realized return	Sharpe	PSR
Dense reference	Soda, Smoke, Hlth, Drugs, Steel, Aero, Gold, Mines	0.0848	0.499	0.969
Best sparse: threshold	Soda, Smoke, Hlth, Drugs, Steel, Aero, Gold, Banks	0.0561	0.444	0.950

Table S4: Representative betting validation slate (`betting_all_20250523_360_m8`, eight selected outcomes). The dense and sparse rows coincide for this slate; the sparse row is the saved `best_sparse:domain_prior` solution.

Method	Selected outcomes	Realized ROI	Brier	Log loss
Dense reference	Napoli vs Cagliari (H); Milan vs Monza (H); Espanol vs Las Palmas (H); Leganes vs Valladolid (H); Real Madrid vs Sociedad (H); Vallecano vs Mallorca (H); Southampton vs Arsenal (A); Torino vs Roma (A)	0.2013	0.122	0.415
Best sparse: domain prior	Napoli vs Cagliari (H); Milan vs Monza (H); Espanol vs Las Palmas (H); Leganes vs Valladolid (H); Real Madrid vs Sociedad (H); Vallecano vs Mallorca (H); Southampton vs Arsenal (A); Torino vs Roma (A)	0.2013	0.122	0.415